

Debiasing alternating minimization for matrix completion and matrix sensing

Abstract

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1 Introduction

Inspiration:

- De-biasing matrix completion: Foucart et al. (2017)
- Some motivation for this particular choice of a way to debias ALS: Hastie et al. (2014)
- Treat alternating minimization as power iteration with error term that goes to zero: Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012)
- Some further insight for previous paper: Hardt (2013)
- Somewhat similar algorithm, but applied to a different problem, and in uniform sampling pattern setting: Hsieh, Natarajan, and Dhillon (2015)

2 Rank factorization

Low-Rank Matrix Factorization problem is:

$$\text{Find } U \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r} \text{ and } V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}, \text{ s.t. } UV^T = X. \quad (\text{LRMF})$$

This problem can be solved using alternating ridge regression, as was done in Hastie et al. (2014):

1. Initialize U_0 and V_0 to random vectors.
2. Set $V_{i+1} = X^T U_i (U_i^T U_i)^{-1}$.
3. Set $U_{i+1} = X V_i (V_i^T V_i)^{-1}$.

3 Matrix sensing

Low-Rank Matrix Sensing problem is:

$$\text{Find } X \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}, \text{ s.t. } \mathcal{A}(X) = b, \text{ rank}(X) \leq k. \quad (\text{LRMS})$$

Let x be vectorized version of X . Define $\mathcal{A}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\mathcal{A}^\perp(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{mn-d}$. We can also think of them as together mapping $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{mn}$, with \mathcal{A} mapping the first d entries, and \mathcal{A}^\perp the last $mn-d$ entries. Hence, using this interpretation, $\langle \mathcal{A}(Z), \mathcal{A}^\perp(Z) \rangle = 0$. \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{A}^\perp are linear measurement operators which we assume satisfy restricted isometry property (RIP):

Definition 3.1. (Recht, Fazel, and Parrilo (2010)) A linear operator $\mathcal{A}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is said to satisfy k -RIP, with δ_k RIP constant, if for all $X \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ s.t. $\text{rank}(X) \leq k$, the following holds:

$$(1 - \delta_k) \|X\|_F^2 \leq \|\mathcal{A}(X)\|_2^2 \leq (1 + \delta_k) \|X\|_F^2. \quad (1)$$

We also define $\mathcal{I} = L \circ \mathcal{A} + K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp$ to be an exact isometry constructed from restricted isometries \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{A}^\perp . I.e., $\|\mathcal{I}(X)\|_2^2 = \|X\|_F^2$.

What this means is that if UV^T is a rank factorization of X , then

$$\|X\|_F^2 = \|\mathcal{I}(X)\|_2^2 = \|\mathcal{I}(UV^T)\|_2^2 = \sum_{i=1}^d (l_i V^T A_i U)^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} (k_j V^T A_j^\perp U)^2$$

Also note that

$$\|X\|_F^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (V^T e_i e_j^T U)^2$$

We can also make use of the following notation:

$$\langle \mathcal{A}(UV^T) | = V^T A_i U \quad \text{and} \quad | \mathcal{A}(UV^T) \rangle = U^T A_i^T V$$

Now, we can express the original rank factorization problem, (LRMF), as the following minimization problem:

$$\min_{U,V} \|\mathcal{I}(UV^\perp - X)\|_2^2 = \min_{U,V} (\|L \circ (\mathcal{A}(UV^T) - b)\|_2^2 + \|K \circ (\mathcal{A}^\perp(UV^T) - b^\perp)\|_2^2) \quad (\text{LRMS}^*)$$

We can think of LRMS* as LRMS, but where before minimizing the problem, we apply an isometry on both the product of dummy variables UV^T , and the original matrix X .

Note: if L and K are scalars, we can considerably simplify the expression by dividing everything by L .

Interesting observation is that in this case we don't even need to care about RIP because overall this transformation doesn't change the problem.

The moment when we do need to care about RIP, though, is when we split the result into two parts (measured and not measured).

To turn this into matrix sensing problem, we should account for the fact that we are not provided with b^\perp .

Hence, following Hastie et al. (2014) intuition, we can replace b^\perp by its approximation that we get from the previous iteration of the algorithm.

We then get the following de-biased alternating minimization algorithm for matrix sensing:

1. Initialize U_0 and V_0 to random matrices.
2. Set $V_{i+1} = \operatorname{argmin}_V \|L \circ [\mathcal{A}(U_i V^T) - b]\|_2^2 + \|K \circ [\mathcal{A}^\perp(U_i(V - V_i)^T)]\|_2^2$.
3. Set $U_{i+1} = \operatorname{argmin}_U \|L \circ [\mathcal{A}(U V_i^T) - b]\|_2^2 + \|K \circ [\mathcal{A}^\perp((U - U_i)V_i^T)]\|_2^2$.

Since the second term is just an estimate, the exact form of linear transformation before optimization becomes important, and hence the RIP.

Intuition: we replace the unknown b^\perp with an estimate, and we weight each component of the second term because we are not completely confident in our estimate.

Hence, the heuristic for choosing the weights should be driven by our confidence in accuracy of entries which are being weighted.

For example, if this was matrix completion, we would be more confident in our estimate for rows and columns which have more measurements.

Also, notice that, in practice, \mathcal{A}^\perp would have much smaller RIP constant than \mathcal{A} , and hence this provides even more motivation to include it in recovery algorithms.

Definition 3.2. (Golub and Van Loan (1996)) Given two matrices $\widehat{U}, \widehat{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times k}$, the (principal angle) distance between the subspaces spanned by the columns of \widehat{U} and \widehat{W} is given by:

$$\text{dist}(\widehat{U}, \widehat{W}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \|U_{\perp}^T W\|_2 = \|W_{\perp}^T U\|_2$$

where U and W are orthonormal bases of the spaces $\text{Span}(\widehat{U})$ and $\text{Span}(\widehat{W})$, respectively. Similarly, U_{\perp} and W_{\perp} are any orthonormal bases of the perpendicular spaces $\text{Span}(U)^{\perp}$ and $\text{Span}(W)^{\perp}$, respectively.

3.1 Rank-1 Case

Let $M = u^* \sigma^* (v^*)^T$ s.t. $u^* \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $\|u^*\|_2 = 1$ and $v^* \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\|v^*\|_2 = 1$. Also note that when \widehat{u} and \widehat{w} are vectors, $\text{dist}(\widehat{u}, \widehat{w}) = 1 - (u^T w)^2$, where $u = \widehat{u} / \|\widehat{u}\|_2$ and $w = \widehat{w} / \|\widehat{w}\|_2$.

In this case our iterative alternating minimization algorithm simplifies considerably:

1. Initialize u_0 and v_0 to random vectors.
2. Set $\widehat{v}^{t+1} = \underset{\widehat{v}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^d [l_i (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_i^T \widehat{v} - \sigma^* u^{*T} A_i^T v^*)]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} [k_j (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} (\widehat{v} - \widehat{v}^t))]^2$.
3. Set $\widehat{u}^{t+1} = \underset{\widehat{u}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^d [l_i (\widehat{u}^T A_i^T \widehat{v}^t - \sigma^* u^{*T} A_i^T v^*)]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} [k_j ((\widehat{u} - \widehat{u}^t)^T A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v}^t)]^2$.

Alternatively, we can write second step as:

$$\widehat{v}^{t+1} = \underset{\widehat{v}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^d [l_i (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_i^T \widehat{v} - \sigma^* u^{*T} A_i^T v^*)]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} [k_j (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v} - \widehat{u}^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v}^t)]^2$$

We can further simplify this by setting $s^t = \|\widehat{u}^t\|_2 \|\widehat{v}^t\|_2$. This would then make it so that $\widehat{u}^t \widehat{v}^{tT} = u^t s^t v^{tT}$:

$$\widehat{v}^{t+1} = \underset{\widehat{v}}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^d [l_i (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_i^T \widehat{v} - \sigma^* u^{*T} A_i^T v^*)]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} [k_j (\widehat{u}^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v} - s^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} v^t)]^2$$

We now have both summands looking very similarly.

Let's investigate iteration step for \widehat{v} . Setting the gradient of it's objective function to zero, we obtain:

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{tT} A_i^T + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^{\perp} u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \right] \|\widehat{u}^t\|_2 \widehat{v}^{t+1} = \sigma^* \left[\sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{*T} A_i^T \right] v^* + s^t \left[\sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^{\perp} u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \right] v^t$$

Let's look at this expression carefully. On the left hand side, we have an exact isometry multiplied by the next iterate of the vector. On the right hand side, we have two summands. One comes from a partial sampling of the original matrix. The second comes from sampling of the remainder of the matrix, using our best current estimate of that matrix.

From here, we can already see that if $u^t = u^*$, $v^t = v^*$, and $s^t = \sigma^*$, we would get something like this (up to an isometry):

$$(u^t u^{tT}) v^{t+1} = (u^t u^{tT}) v^t$$

Actually, let's simplify left side accordingly:

$$[u^t u^{tT}] \|\widehat{u}^t\|_2 \widehat{v}^{t+1} = \sigma^* \left[\sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{*T} A_i^T \right] v^* + s^t \left[\sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^{\perp} u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \right] v^t$$

Now, let

$$B = \left[\sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{tT} A_i^T + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^{\perp} u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \right]$$

and

$$C = \left[\sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{*T} A_i^T + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} \frac{k_j^2 \|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} A_j^\perp u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v}^t v^{*T} \right]$$

Then, following Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012), we massage the problem as power method plus error term:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\widehat{u}^t\|_2 \widehat{v}^{t+1} &= \sigma^* B^{-1} C v^*, \\ &= \underbrace{\langle u^*, u^t \rangle \sigma^* v^*}_{\text{Power Method}} - \underbrace{B^{-1} (\langle u^*, u^t \rangle B - C) \sigma^* v^*}_{\text{Error Term}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Now, Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012) already showed that the error terms goes to zero as u^t gets closer to u^* for the case when $k_j = 0$ for all j . Therefore, our goal is to show that we can in fact make the second term go to zero faster if k_j is chosen appropriately.

Lemma 3.3. (Extends Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012) for $k_j \neq 0$) Consider the error term defined in (2) and let $K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp$ satisfy 2-RIP with constant δ_2 . Then,

$$\|B^{-1} (\langle u^*, v^t \rangle B - C) v^*\| \leq \left| \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} - \langle u^t, u^* \rangle \right| + 3\delta_2 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2^2}{\sigma^{*2}}}$$

(not correct)

Proof. Using definition of the spectral norm:

$$\|B^{-1} (\langle u^*, u^t \rangle B - C) v^*\| \leq \|B^{-1}\|_2 \cdot \|\langle u^*, u^t \rangle B - C\|_2 \cdot \|v^*\|_2. \quad (3)$$

Now, smallest eigenvalue of B , i.e., $\lambda_{\min}(B)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\min}(B) &= \min_{\|z\|=1} z^T B z = \min_{\|z\|=1} \sum_{i=1}^d z^T l_i^2 A_i u^t u^{tT} A_i^T z + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} z^T k_j^2 A_j^\perp u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} z \\ &= \min_{\|z\|=1} \sum_i \text{Tr}(A_i l_i u^t z^T) \text{Tr}(A_i l_i u^t z^T) + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} \text{Tr}(A_j^\perp k_j u^t z^T) \text{Tr}(A_j^\perp k_j u^t z^T) \\ &= \min_{\|z\|=1} \langle L \circ \mathcal{A}(u^t z^T), L \circ \mathcal{A}(u^t z^T) \rangle + \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T) \rangle \\ &= \min_{\|z\|=1} \langle \mathcal{I}(u^t z^T), \mathcal{I}(u^t z^T) \rangle = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where we can combine inner products together because for any Z , $\langle \mathcal{A}(Z), \mathcal{A}^\perp(Z) \rangle = 0$.

The last equality comes from the fact that $\mathcal{A} + K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp$ is an isomorphism. This is an improvement from Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012), where they had an upper bound of $1 - 3\delta_2$ instead.

In fact, we can say something even stronger: B is an isometry. I.e., all its eigenvalues are equal to 1.

Using 4,

$$\|B^{-1}\|_2 \leq 1. \quad (5)$$

Now, consider

$$\begin{aligned} G &= \langle u^*, u^t \rangle B - C \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i (\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t u^{tT} - u^t u^{*T}) A_i^T + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^\perp \left(\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t u^{tT} A_i^{\perp T} - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t u^{tT} A_i^{\perp T} \widehat{v}^t v^{*T} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^d l_i^2 A_i u^t (\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^{tT} - u^{*T}) A_i^T + \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} k_j^2 A_j^\perp u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \left(\langle u^*, u^t \rangle - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} \widehat{v}^t v^{*T} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Using definition of the spectral norm:

$$\begin{aligned}
\|G\|_2 &= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} z^T G y \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \sum_{i=1}^d z^T l_i^2 A_i u^t (\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t - u^*)^T A_i^T y + \langle u^*, u^t \rangle \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} z^T k_j^2 A_j^\perp u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} y \\
&\quad - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} \sum_{j=1}^{nm-d} z^T k_j^2 A_j^\perp u^t u^{tT} A_j^{\perp T} \widehat{v}^t v^{*T} y \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle L \circ \mathcal{A}(u^t z^T), L \circ \mathcal{A}(\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t - u^*) y^T \rangle + \langle u^*, u^t \rangle \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t y^T) \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle \mathcal{I}(u^t z^T), \mathcal{I}(\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t y^T) - L \circ \mathcal{A}(u^* y^T) - K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(\frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle \mathcal{I}(u^t z^T), \mathcal{I}(\langle u^*, u^t \rangle u^t y^T - u^* y^T) + K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^* y^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle \mathcal{I}(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^* y^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^* y^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&= \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^* y^T) \rangle - \langle K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(u^t z^T), K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp(\frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle \\
&\leq \max_{\|z\|=\|y\|=1} 3\delta_2 \|u^t z^T\|_F (\|u^* y^T\|_F + \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} \|u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}\|_F) + \langle u^{tT} u^*, z^T y \rangle - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} \langle u^{tT} u^t, z^T \widehat{v}^* v^{*T} y \rangle \\
&\leq \left| \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} - \langle u^t, u^* \rangle \right| + 3\delta_2 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2^2}{\sigma^{*2}}} \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

(last bound not correct) where the last inequality follows by using Lemma 3.4. For comparison, Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012) got a bound of $3\delta_2 \sqrt{1 - \langle u^t, u^* \rangle^2}$ instead.

Where we have used $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}^\perp \rangle = 0$. Also we set δ_2 to be $2k$ -RIP constant of $K \circ \mathcal{A}^\perp$ (as opposed to \mathcal{A} in Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012)). This gives a number of improvements: (1) \mathcal{A}^\perp should be closer to an isometry as opposed to \mathcal{A} simply because it has more dimensions, and (2) we can weight it by K to improve its isometry properties. Second argument becomes of high importance if for example we have non-uniform sampling, with certain projections taken more often than others, as is the case in many real-world datasets. \square

Let's investigate this further:

$$\langle \mathcal{A}(u^t z^T), \mathcal{A}(u^* y^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) \rangle$$

Let

$$X = u^t z^T + u^* y^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}$$

.

Expanding:

$$X = u^t(z^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) + u^* y^T$$

We see that rank of X is at most $2k$. Hence, using $2k$ -RIP of \mathcal{A} :

$$\|\mathcal{A}(X)\|_2^2 \leq (1 + \delta) \|u^t(z^T - \frac{\|\widehat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} y^T v^* \widehat{v}^{tT}) + u^* y^T\|_F^2$$

Hence:

$$\sum_i (\text{Tr}(A_i u^t z^T) + \text{Tr}[A_i (u^* y^T - \frac{\|\hat{u}^t\|_2}{\sigma^*} u^t y^T v^* \hat{v}^t)])^2 \leq (1 + \delta) \quad (123)$$

Lemma 3.4. (Jain, Netrapalli, and Sanghavi (2012)) Suppose $\mathcal{A}(\cdot)$ satisfies $2k$ -RIP with constant δ_{2k} . Then, for any $U_1, U_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times k}$ and $V_1, V_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}$, we have the following:

$$|\langle \mathcal{A}(U_1 V_1^T), \mathcal{A}(U_2 V_2^T) \rangle - \text{Tr}(U_2^T U_1 V_1^T V_2)| \leq 3\delta_{2k} \|U_1 V_1^T\|_F \|U_2 V_2^T\|_F \quad (8)$$

4 Matrix completion

Low-Rank Matrix Completion problem is:

$$\text{Find } X \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}, \text{ s.t. } P_\Omega(X) = P_\Omega(M), \text{ rank}(X) \leq k. \quad (\text{LRMC})$$

4.1 Convergence proof, based on Hastie et al. (2014)

Optimization problems:

$$\underset{M}{\text{minimize}} \quad H(M) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - M)\|_F^2 + \lambda \|M\|_* \quad (9)$$

$$\underset{A, B}{\text{minimize}} \quad F(A, B) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - AB^T)\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|A\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|B\|_F^2 \quad (10)$$

Surrogate functions, as introduced by Hastie et al. (2014):

$$Q_A(Z_1|A, B) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - Z_1 B^T) + P_\Omega^\perp(AB^T - Z_1 B^T)\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|Z_1\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|B\|_F^2 \quad (11)$$

$$Q_B(Z_2|A, B) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - AZ_2^T) + P_\Omega^\perp(AB^T - AZ_2^T)\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|A\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|Z_2\|_F^2 \quad (12)$$

Our modification of surrogate functions:

$$Q_A^*(Z_1|A, B) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - Z_1 B^T) + P_\Omega^\perp(AB^T - Z_1 B^T) \circ \frac{1}{K}\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|Z_1\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|B\|_F^2 \quad (13)$$

$$Q_B^*(Z_2|A, B) := \frac{1}{2} \|P_\Omega(X - AZ_2^T) + P_\Omega^\perp(AB^T - AZ_2^T) \circ \frac{1}{K}\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|A\|_F^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|Z_2\|_F^2 \quad (14)$$

It is then easy to check that convergence argument by Hastie et al. (2014) still holds.

References

Foucart, Simon, Deanna Needell, Yaniv Plan, and Mary Wootters. 2017. “De-biasing low-rank projection for matrix completion.” In *Wavelets and Sparsity XVII*, edited by Yue M. Lu, Dimitri Van De Ville, and Manos Papadakis, 10394:269–81. International Society for Optics; Photonics; SPIE. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2275004>.

Golub, GH, and CF Van Loan. 1996. “Matrix Computations 3rd Edition the John Hopkins University Press.” *Baltimore, MD*.

- Hardt, Moritz. 2013. “Understanding Alternating Minimization for Matrix Completion.” <http://arxiv.org/abs/1312.0925>.
- Hastie, Trevor, Rahul Mazumder, Jason Lee, and Reza Zadeh. 2014. “Matrix Completion and Low-Rank Svd via Fast Alternating Least Squares.” <http://arxiv.org/abs/1410.2596>.
- Hsieh, Cho-Jui, Nagarajan Natarajan, and Inderjit Dhillon. 2015. “PU Learning for Matrix Completion.” In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2445–53. PMLR.
- Jain, Prateek, Praneeth Netrapalli, and Sujay Sanghavi. 2012. “Low-Rank Matrix Completion Using Alternating Minimization.” <http://arxiv.org/abs/1212.0467>.
- Recht, Benjamin, Maryam Fazel, and Pablo A Parrilo. 2010. “Guaranteed Minimum-Rank Solutions of Linear Matrix Equations via Nuclear Norm Minimization.” *SIAM Review* 52 (3): 471–501.